

Brief Research Report

Determinants of Home Economics Lecturers' Psychological Work Hazards in Southeast Nigerian Universities

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Abstract: Nigerian schools are diverse, resulting in psychological hazards for most workers, particularly teachers. It is common for teachers to suffer from psychosocial work hazards in Nigeria, yet no research has been conducted to examine how teachers' demographics influence such hazards. Therefore, this study investigated the psychological hazards faced by Home Economics lecturers based on their age and location. The researcher employed an ex-post fact design and a quantitative approach to study 62 Home Economics lecturers in southeast Nigerian universities. In the study, researchers devised a 28-item questionnaire to collect data about work deviant behavior. A reliability index of 0.76 was estimated for the items of the questionnaire. The data were analyzed using analysis of variance. The findings revealed a high prevalence of Psychological job hazards among Home Economics lecturers in Southeast Universities. Psychological job hazards of Home Economics lecturers were not significantly influenced by their age or location. This implies that psychosocial job risks are not greatly influenced by the age and location of Home Economics lecturers. In conclusion, it was recommended that secondary school authorities consider teacher age and location when assessing psychosocial work hazards.

Keywords: Age, Home Economics Lecturers, Location, Psychosocial Work Hazards

1. Introduction

Workers may be exposed to psychological risks and hazards as a result of their professions. The health and wellbeing of workers can be affected by a variety of factors, including stress, fatigue, bullying, aggression, hostility, harassment, and burnout. A workplace danger can result in health injury due to various risk factors (such as alcohol or drug abuse, or poor change management). The psychosocial risks associated with bullying, violence, and job insecurity in the workplace are increasing worldwide (Cheng, 2018). There is no doubt that workplace stress contributes in large part to psychological distress and that workplace psychosocial conditions have a significant impact on workers' health (Liang et al., 2018). Work-related stress and negative psychosocial work conditions are resulting in increased levels of burnout among workers (Misiak et al., 2020). There has been very little research on health and safety issues in the teaching profession despite the fact that teachers have a variety of concerns (Ng et al., 2019). There are several psychosocial work hazards that are increasing around the world (Cheng, 2018), such as bullying and violence in the workplace, job insecurity, and financial uncertainty. In recent decades, psychosocial work conditions have been well documented as a significant source of psychosocial stress at work (Liang et al., 2018). A growing number of workers are experiencing burnout because of poor psychosocial working conditions and the stress they experience at work (Misiak et al., 2020).

There has been very little research on health and safety problems that teachers experience in the teaching profession, despite the fact that teachers have a variety of health and safety concerns (Ng et al., 2019). The workplace had psychological hazards for 72.9% of Putrajaya teachers (Mohd Anuar et al., 2016). A lack of resources and equipment (50.37%) and poor communication and staff attitude (67.72%) were the most common psychosocial work hazards among Nigerian workers (Onigbogi & Banerjee, 2019). Psychosocial hazards affected 62.2 percent of workers at the University of Port Harcourt in Nigeria, with workplace verbal abuse accounting for 43.9 percent (Kennedy, 2018). There are a number of psychosocial work risks that have increased over time, causing anxiety, such as employment expectations, control, status, and relationships (Wray & Kinman, 2020). This resulted in the establishment of this study, which examined the psychological hazards teachers face based on their demographics.

Psychosocial work hazards were found to be positively linked to authoritarian and laissez-faire leadership styles in most studies (Feijó et al., 2019). Teachers coped with stress better by managing their jobs and receiving social support (Ibrahim et al., 2021). There are many factors that may influence psychosocial workplace conditions (Azizah et al., 2016), including gender, education level, salary, job title, and length of service. In addition to age, gender, and job demands, inadequate job control significantly affected psychosocial work hazards (Kabito & Mekonnen, 2020). Psychosocial risks kindergarten teachers face at work are significantly influenced by their age and qualifications (Echo et al., 2019). According to Mohd Anuar et al. (2016), gender was strongly associated with psychological work hazards among teachers in Putrajaya, even after controlling for other characteristics like age, marital status, and other employment activities.

The factors associated with elevated psychological job risks include age, gender, the job status of the father, school rank, not living with both biological parents, perceived family disharmony, low self-esteem, and depression (Lee et al., 2021). It was found that exposure to psychosocial work risks and the prevalence of work-related disorders are related to both formal and informal teachers (Gimeno Ruiz De Porras et al., 2017). The number of reports of suspected psychosocial work disorders was higher for female principals than male principals, even though school level was not linked with reports (Persson et al., 2021). Psychosocial work disorder symptoms were associated with the work experience of male principals (Persson et al., 2021). There is a substantial relationship between psychosocial workplace factors and the age of workers (Xu et al., 2022). There are several factors that influence work-related psychological risks among Italian workers, including their gender, education level, and age (La Torre et al., 2018).

There is a direct correlation between work-related stress and marital status (Wireko-Gyebi & Ametepeh, 2016). According to Alias et al. (2020), age and gender were significantly associated with psychological employment risks among Malaysian primary school teachers. The exposure to psychosocial components at work and in job-related health was not significantly correlated with gender, according to some work organization models (Migliore et al., 2021). In contrast, high physical demands and moderately high work-family conflict led to elevated psychosocial work hazards among men (Weale et al., 2021).

1.1. Statement of Problem

Nigerian schools are diverse, resulting in psychological hazards for most workers, particularly teachers. It is common for teachers to suffer from psychosocial work hazards in Nigeria, yet no research has been conducted to examine how teachers' demographics influence such hazards. Despite that a number of studies have been conducted regarding the factors affecting workers' psychosocial work hazards in different parts of the world, as indicated in the previous studies, none of such studies considered the case of the Nigerian Home Economics lecturers. This gap in literature necessitated this research.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

The general purpose of this research is to determine the determinants of psychosocial work hazards of home economics lecturers in the Southeast Universities. Specific purpose is to:

- (a) Influence of location on psychosocial work hazards of home economics lecturers in the Southeast Universities
- (b) Influence of age on psychosocial work hazards of home economics lecturers in the Southeast Universities

1.3. Research Questions

The following research question guided the study:

- (a) What is the influence of location on psychosocial work hazards of home economics lecturers in the Southeast Universities?
- (b) What is the influence of age on psychosocial work hazards of home economics lecturers in the Southeast Universities?

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

This study followed the scientific research paradigm because it made inferences based on hypothesis testing. Based on this scientific study paradigm, a quantitative research technique was used. A study of ex-post facto research design was used to examine how the ages and locations of Home Economics lecturers are influenced by their psychological job hazards. Researchers have used similar paradigms, methodologies, and research designs in similar studies over the past few years (Ugwuanyi, Okeke, & Ageda, 2020; Ugwuanyi, Okeke & Njeze, 2020).

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

A copy of the ethical approval letter issued by the Faculty of Education of the University of Nigeria, as well as permission to conduct the study in the universities, were obtained by the researchers in accordance with the university's ethical rules. In this case, the American Psychological Association's standards for conducting human-related research are followed. Informed consent forms were given to participants before data collection began.

2.2. Area of the Study

This research was conducted in the southeast states of Nigeria. These states are Abia, Anambra, Ebonyi, Enugu and Imo States. This region of Nigeria is populated mostly by the Igbo speaking people of Nigeria.

2.3. Population and Sample

The study involved 62 Home Economics lecturers from southeast Nigerian universities. In the southeast, federal universities were sampled using a simple random sampling technique and the participants were purposively selected from such Universities.

2.4. Instrument for Data Collection and Study Procedure

For the purpose of determining the demographic characteristics of the primary school teachers participating in the study, researchers created a demographic profile questionnaire. Among the demographic characteristics of the participants are their age, gender, position in the workplace, qualification, marital status, and location. Kristensen et al. (2005) conducted an investigation using the Copenhagen Psychosocial Questionnaire (COPSOQ) which was adapted for this study. As a self-report questionnaire, the COPSOQ evaluates psychosocial aspects such as stress, health, well-being, and personality (coping style, sense of coherence, etc.). For the purpose of determining the measure's face validity, experts in educational psychology, measurements, and assessments from the researchers' universities were consulted. Experts assessed the measurement elements for their

relevance to the study's goals. As part of the research process, they were asked to provide suggestions that would assist the researchers. Following expert judgements, the draft instruments were revised into their final form. For the purpose of assessing the measure's reliability, 20 Home Economics lecturers in universities in Ebonyi state were subjected to COPSOQ trials. According to the Cronbach alpha method, COPSOQ's reliability value was 0.76 for the Nigerian sample.

2.5. Data Collection Technique

A gatekeeper letter and ethical approval were obtained from the universities that participated in the study before data collection began. Approximately four weeks were needed to complete the data collection. There was a 20-minute time limit on each participant's measures. After completing the forms, they picked up the completed copies on the spot.

2.6. Data Analysis Technique

In order to analyze the data, descriptive and inferential statistics were used. In order to answer the study questions, mean data were analyzed, while variance was used to test hypotheses. Similar statistical approaches have been used by many researchers (Ugwuanyi et al., 2021; Agboeze et al., 2021; Ene et al., 2021).

3. Results and Discussion

Figure 1: Bar chart representation of the levels of psychological work hazards among Home Economics Lecturers

Figure 1 shows a high prevalence (67.7%) of psychological work hazards among Home Economics lecturers in Southeast Universities.

Table 1: Mean analysis of the influence of age on Home Economics lecturers' psychosocial work hazards

Age of Lecturers	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
26-35 years	20	104.55	30.76
36-45 years	20	109.80	12.72
46 years and above	22	108.23	18.52

There was a mean psychosocial work risk of ($M = 104.55$, $SD = 30.76$) for Home Economics lecturers under the age of 26-35 years (Table 1), a mean psychosocial work risk of ($M = 109.80$, $SD = 12.72$) for Home Economics lecturers between the ages of 36 and 45 and a mean psychosocial work risk of ($M = 108.52$, $SD = 18.52$) for lecturers within 46 years and above.

Table 2: Analysis of variance of the influence of age on Home Economics lecturers' psychosocial work hazards

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	291.341	2	145.671	.304	.739
Within Groups	28252.014	59	478.848		
Total	28543.355	61			

Statistical analysis shows that the age of lecturers in Home Economics does not influence their psychological job hazards, $F(2, 59) = 304$, $p = .739$. This means that psychological job risks are not dependent on the age of Home Economics lecturers.

Table 3: Mean analysis of the influence of location on Home Economics lecturers' psychosocial work hazards

Location of Lecturers	n	Mean	Std. Deviation
Urban	39	109.41	19.57
Rural	23	104.39	24.88

In Table 3, it is shown that the average psychosocial work hazards of Home Economics lecturers at urban schools were ($M = 109.41$, $SD = 19.57$), whereas the average psychosocial work hazards at rural schools were ($M = 104.39$, $SD = 24.88$). There were higher variations in psychosocial work hazards scores for rural teachers than urban teachers, as evidenced by the standard deviations of 19.57 and 24.88 for urban and rural lecturers, respectively.

Table 4: Analysis of variance of the influence of location on Home Economics lecturers' psychosocial work hazards

	Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	364.441	1	364.441	.776	.382
Within Groups	28178.914	60	469.649		
Total	28543.355	61			

Based on Table 4, the location of Home Economics lecturers does not have a significant impact on their psychological job hazards, with $F(1, 60) = .776, p = .382$. Lecturers in Home Economics do not face any psychological risks because of the location of their places of work.

Home Economics lecturers' psychosocial work hazards were examined based on their school location and age. Psychosocial work hazards among Home Economics lecturers were not significantly influenced by school location or age. In other words, the location of the school and the age of the lecturers do not have a significant effect on their psychosocial health. Further studies have confirmed these findings, showing no impact on psychosocial occupational hazards of gender, marital status, years of teaching experience, and employment position. The psychological workplace dangers faced by women with few work–family conflicts, for example, are smaller than those faced by men (Weale et al., 2021). Principals of female schools reported more symptoms of suspected psychosocial work disorders than principals of male schools, despite the fact that school level did not seem to be associated with the likelihood of such disorders (Persson et al., 2021).

Xu et al. (2022), however, found that the psychosocial factors at work had a strong relationship with worker age, correlating these results. Age is a factor that influences the psychosocial risks kindergarten teachers face at work (Echo et al., 2019). According to La Torre et al. (2018), Italian workers' age predicts their psychological hazards at work. Primary school teachers' age correlates significantly with psychological occupational hazards in Malaysia, according to Alias et al. (2020). A high job demand, an inadequate workplace control, and the age of the worker were significant factors influencing psychosocial work dangers (Kabito & Mekonnen, 2020). In the workplace, workers' age was found to be highly related to their risk of psychological risks (Lee et al., 2021).

Psychosocial work disorder symptoms were linked to the work experience of male principals (Persson et al., 2021). Occupational stress is influenced by both marital status and work environment (Wireko-Gyebi & Ametepah, 2016). Psychosocial occupational hazards were strongly associated with teachers' educational degrees (Azizah et al., 2016). Psychological risks associated with work are strongly influenced by the educational levels of Italian workers (La Torre et al., 2018). It appears that the relationships between teachers' demographic traits and psychosocial occupational hazards are irregular. In light of this situation, more empirical research is needed. Future researchers are therefore encouraged to replicate this work in the same or a different context in order to compare the results to what has already been found. Psychosocial workplace hazards are related to teacher demographic profiles, which will help to understand these relationships better.

4. Conclusion

This study found that the location of the school and the age of Home Economics lecturers did not affect their psychosocial hazards at work. This study concluded that school location and age do not influence the psychological occupational hazards faced by Home Economics lecturers. Psychosocial dangers at work are not determined by the age or location of Home Economics lecturers.

Acknowledgements

The authors acknowledge all the study participants and the relevant authorities that made the research feasible.

Conflict of Interest

Not applicable

Author Contributions

The author solely carried out the development of this manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The data for this study are at the custody of the author.

Funding Information

No funding was available for this research.

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